

Residents' Perception of Seafood as a Tourism Product

Nelly S. Maliva, Juliana G. Wilbard,
Bahati D. Mbilinyi, Donatus P. Massawe & Kezia H. Mkwizu

About the Authors

- ★ Nelly S. Maliva, University of Dar es Salaam Business School, Email: nmaliva@yahoo.co.uk
- ★★ Juliana G. Wilbard, Recca Investment, Email: julswil2004@yahoo.com
- ★★★ Bahati D. Mbilinyi, The Open University of Tanzania, Email: bmbilinyi@yahoo.com
- ★★★★ Donatus P. Massawe, University of Dar es Salaam Business School, Email: donatuspeter@gmail.com
- ★★★★★ Kezia H. Mkwizu, corresponding author, Open University of Tanzania, Email: kmkwizu@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Tourism product is one of the concepts that have attracted attention of scholars in tourism studies. Although tourism is growing, the development of tourism products is a challenge for various destinations including coastal areas which widely depend on coastal tourism. One of the abundant products in coastal areas is seafood. Studies related to coastal areas in tourism have concentrated on food in general such as dining experiences while others in relation to tourists' perception of services quality in the hospitality industry but very few have researched on residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product within destinations. Those studies conducted on seafood mainly focused on tourists' perception on seafood offered and scantily address issues related to residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product. The approach of this study was qualitative and captured in-depth information on whether or not residents perceive seafood as a tourism product. The study was carried out in Dar es Salaam City in Tanzania. Interviews were conducted with respondents who were selected through convenience sampling at the Kivukoni fish market. The result of this study revealed that awareness and participation were the core factors in residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product. The outcome of this study can contribute to addressing economic growth which is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by linking seafood and tourism. Also at the national level, the tourism sector can use the information of this study to build awareness of seafood as tourism product in coastal areas of Tanzania.

Keyword: *residents' perception, seafood, tourism product*

JEL Code: M39

CIATATION:

Maliva, Nelly S., Wilbard, Juliana G., Mbilinyi, Bahati D., Massawe, Donatus P. and Mkwizu, Kezia H. (2018). "Residents' Perception of Seafood as a Tourism Product." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 4, No. 3, pp. 68-76. (Jul. – Sep. 2018); ISSN: 2415-0371.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism plays an important role globally and contributes significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of many countries. WTTC (2017) showed that total contribution of tourism and travel to GDP was USD 7,613.3 billion worldwide in 2016. Although tourism is growing, a study by Ardabili, Rasouli, Daryani, Molaie and Sharegi (2011) stated that little attention is given to food in tourism and hence food is treated as secondary and minor role in the tourism industry. Another study by Galvez, Guzman, Buiza and Viruel (2017) found that foreign tourists in Peru exhibit dimensions of new food experience and socialization as motivation for food satisfaction. Generally there are scarce studies on seafood as a tourism product.

Tourism product is one of the concepts that have attracted attention of scholars in tourism studies. Despite the growth in tourism, the development of tourism products is a challenge for various destinations including coastal areas which widely depend on coastal tourism. One of the abundant products in coastal areas is seafood. Studies related to coastal areas in tourism have concentrated on food in general including dining experiences (Ardabili *et al.*, 2011; Horng & Tsai, 2012; Galvez *et al.*, 2017; Mbilinyi, 2017). Further studies by Mas (2015) in Spain, and Su, Wall and Wang (2017) in China looked at seafood in relation to island development and consumption and not particularly the residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product within destinations. On the other hand, Ukwayi, Eja and Unawanede (2012) assessed tourist perception on service quality delivery in the hospitality industry at Cross River State in Nigeria. Generally, studies conducted on seafood mainly focused on tourists' perception on seafood offered and scantily address issues related to residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product since they are one of the stakeholders of coastal tourism.

Tanzania is endowed with world class coastal attractions (Tanzania Coastal Management Partnership, 2001). However, the diversification to coastal attractions has not received much attention from the perspective of giving attention to seafood as a tourism product. A number of recent studies in Tanzania have examined various issues on coastal tourism in locations such as Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Tanga and Zanzibar with research related to leakages, festivals, women in tourism, customer relationship, food, airline customers satisfaction and heritage (Anderson, 2013; Mgonja, Backman & Backman, 2014; Jani, 2016; Maliva, 2016; Maliva & Jani, 2017; Wilbard & Jani, 2017; Mbilinyi, 2017; Jani & Naji, 2017; Singa'mbi & Lwoga, 2017) but there is limited literature on seafood as a tourism product. A recent study by Mbilinyi (2017) conducted in Tanzania was interested in the dining experiences of tourists food consumption whereby the finding showed that determinants such as food quality and food services were identified as significant in the total dining experience of tourists.

As more destinations still need to increase the number of tourists visiting their attractions, it is important for studies to consider diversification of research in various areas including food in tourism. In order for Tanzania to embrace the abundant tourism resources, this paper therefore, aim to explore residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product. Specifically, the study identified core factors of residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product in terms of awareness and participation. This study is crucial in efforts to boost coastal tourism and contribute to diversification from wildlife-based attractions to seafood attractions in tourism.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concepts Definition

2.1.1 Perception

The concept of perception has been defined in many studies (Swarbrooke & Horner, 1999; Solomon, 2011; Robbins, 2005; Stevenson & Waite, 2012; Araria, Carmelo & Leon, 2013; Lamb, Hair & McDaniel, 2014). The study by Swarbrooke and Horner (1999) defined perception as the subjective interpretation by individuals of the data available to them to provide opinions of and attitudes towards products, places and organizations. Stevenson and Waite (2012) referred perception as the ability to see, hear and become aware of something through senses. On the other

hand, Lamb et al. (2014) described perception as a process by which people select, organize and interpret stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture. In this paper, perception is defined as the awareness of residents and their participation in relation to seafood as a tourism product. Furthermore, in this study the residents are “fish vendors”.

2.1.2 Tourism Product

Various studies have provided the definition of tourism product (Xu, 2010; Candela & Figini, 2012; Gortan-Carlin & Krajnovic, 2016; Kozhevnikova, 2016). Tourism product can consist of cultural products that are heritage, fashion and also be referred to as music (Carlin & Krajnovic, 2016). Another scholar defined tourism product as a bundle of goods and services in tourism (Candela & Figini, 2012). Tourism product has also been defined from the marketing perspective both tangible and intangible because it caters for tourism needs and promoted in the marketplace (Xu, 2010). Another study in Nepal found that Chitwan National Park is a unique product in tourism (Kafle, 2014). In Tanzania, various studies have been done on national parks such as Kitulo, Udzungwa as well as Saadani National Park which is also a unique national park since it is the only national park in Tanzania which borders the ocean (Mkwizu, 2016, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c, 2018; Quintero, 2018). This paper defines tourism product as seafood including various species of fish and fish products.

2.2 Theoretical Literature Review

Theoretical framework for this study is grounded on the theory of planned behaviour which was developed by Ajzen (1991). Theory of planned behaviour assumes individual's behaviour is underpinned by three constructs which are intention, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991; Schultz, 2014, Meng, Zhang & Pan, 2015). The intentions to behave or attitude are predicted through application (Hus, 2014). Subjective norms refer to social pressure or influence from family, friends and significant others (Ajzen, 1991; Hsu, 2014; Schultz, 2014). Perceived behaviour is referred to ease of difficulty of performing the behaviour due to past experiences or expected impediments and obstacles (Hsu, 2014). Since this study assumes that individual residents' attitude towards seafood as a tourist product, and their beliefs on the potential of seafood and participation in seafood activities in developing seafood as a tourism product would ultimately result into an intention to attract tourists into seafood tourism as well as involving more residents to participate into seafood activities.

Studies have used theory of planned behaviour to explain some food related behaviours. The study by Hsu (2014) used theory of planned behaviour to study food tourism by examining food behaviour and argued that personal traits such as food neophobia and sensation-seeking influenced food tourism in relation to people's food choice behaviour. Hsu (2014) found that new experience, good reputation, affordable price and cultural experience were the major reasons associated with purchase of Taiwanese traditional food. Similarly Schultz (2014) utilized theory of planned behaviour to research not just food but within the field of tourism by focusing on participation in sustainable tourism certification programs, and found that attitudes played a major role as to why Bed and Breakfast (B&B) operators engage in sustainable tourism certification programs.

Hence this study adopts theory of planned behaviour to guide in exploring perception of seafood as a tourism product by residents. Furthermore, this paper argues that residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product is related to awareness and participation as the perceived ability of seafood as a tourism product. Using theory of planned behaviour enables this study to explore whether residents perceive seafood as a tourism product or not. In theory of planned behaviour, the perceived behaviour is how easy or hard it is for a person to perform a behaviour or rather a person's ability to perform a behaviour (Conner & Armitage, 1998; Schultz, 2014).

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Previous studies on perception and food tourism exist including Xu (2010), Ardabili *et al* (2011), Kumar, Sakthivel and Rananathan (2013), Galvez *et al* (2017), and Mbilinyi (2017). Xu (2010)

focused on the concept of perception by using Smith's framework and found that tangible physical plant was considered to be the core of tourism product in China. Kumar *et al* (2013) conducted a research in India to understand local residents' perception and attitude towards model tourism village. The study by Kumar *et al* (2013) used principal component analysis and rotated component matrix to analyse data. The results showed that those residents benefitting from tourism do support tourism compare to those residents who do not benefit from tourism.

Another study conducted in India by Rajesh (2013) developed a theoretical model on the impact of tourist perceptions, destination image and tourists satisfaction on destination loyalty. Rajesh (2013) found that tourist perception was influenced by factors such as historical and cultural attractions, destination affordability, travel environment, infrastructure, entertainment and natural attractions. Again the study by Rejesh (2013) focuses on tourist perception while this is interested on residents' perception. Perception in tourism has also been studied by other scholars such as Dolnicar and Huybers (2010). In the study by Dolnicar and Huybers (2010) done in Australia, shows that the research concern was on tourists and their perception on different cities like Sydney and Canberra. The application of non-parametric technique called the Perception Based Market Segmentation (PBMS) enabled the study to identify perceptions on different cities by tourists and these perceptions include statements such as "it is vibrant", "has a pleasant climate" and "is friendly" (Dolnicar & Huybers, 2010).

A similar study by Gnanapala (2015) also investigated tourists' perception and the focus was on destination management. Hence most studies in tourism have conducted research on perception with majority on destination management, cities and destination loyalty. Few studies like Xu (2010) in China and Grudda (2010) in New Zealand investigated perception on tourism product and seafood. Although Robinson and Hite (2015) did a study in the US on Gulf Coast seafood, the interest was on tourists' preference and perception in relation to safety of seafood. The use of factor analysis and bivariate probit estimation showed that travellers to the Gulf Coast value fresh seafood for reasons of health, and perceive the seafood to be safe (Robinson & Hite, 2015). Therefore, labeling of seafood was a major issue in seafood for consumers (Robinson & Hite, 2015).

Su *et al* (2017) did a study in China and used a qualitative approach to investigate residents' perception on fishing tourism and island development. Su *et al* (2017) analysed the text and photographic data using thematic analysis and found that majority of respondents had high school and university education. Further results indicated that the residents provide free fishing gear and barbecue appliances to visitors to have fun in fishing and barbecue.

In Tanzania, Mbilinyi (2017) identified determinants of the tourists' food dining experiences and revealed quality dining to be an important factor. The main suggestion of Mbilinyi (2017) study was diversification of tourism products by including food tourism and seafood inclusive as tourism product. Therefore, to add knowledge in tourism studies, this study explored residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product.

3. DATA & METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional design is adopted in this study. The paradigm approach of this study was qualitative and therefore captured in-depth information on awareness and participation to explore residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product. The study was conducted in Dar es Salaam City at Kivukoni fish market in Tanzania. The Kivukoni fish market was selected as the study area for this paper because it is the largest fish market in Dar es Salaam. The unit of analysis is fish vendors as residents. Interviews were face to face and done on one to one basis not as a group in order to obtain rich information.

As the population of fish vendors is not known, the respondents were selected using convenience sampling and a saturation level of 6 respondents was achieved. The concept of perception is adopted from the studies by Ajzen (1991), Schutlz (2014) and Meng *et al* (2015) in order to explore residents' perception of seafood as a tourism product. The respondents were asked on their perception in terms of their awareness of seafood as a tourism product, and their

participation in seafood as a tourism product. The qualitative data collected was subjected to content analysis. The data was recorded on a note book and then content analysis involved coding the answers in order to generate themes on awareness and participation.

4. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

Findings on the profile of the six respondents are shown on Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents

No.	Age	Gender	Income per day	Education
1	Above 50	Male	Above 100,000 TZS	secondary
2	Above 45	Male	Above 100,000 TZS	secondary
3	25-35	Male	Above 45,000 TZS	primary
4	Above 35	Male	Above 50,000 TZS	secondary
5	Above 25	Female	Above 45,000 TZS	primary
6	Above 35	Female	Above 65,000 TZS	primary

Source: Field data, 2018

The above profile suggests that most of the respondents were male, from 35 years to above 50 years, earn income above 100,000 TZS and have a secondary education. The findings differ from Su *et al* (2017) which shows that majority of the interviewed respondents were high school and university graduates.

Interview findings presented in Table 2 showed subthemes that emerged from the interview.

Table 2. Awareness and Participation

Respondents	Sub-themes for Awareness	Sub-themes for Participation
1 st respondent	New face in the fish market means a tourist, I show fish to tourists, smile and say “karibu”	Fish tasting, trust, convincing, fish education, persuasion, discounts, livelihood
2 nd respondent	I show fish to tourists. Being friendly	Discounts, fish tasting, convincing, livelihood
3 rd respondent	Charge more to tourists. A welcome smile	Discounts
4 th respondent	Friendly to customers	Convincing the fish is fresh and good, to make ends meet
5 th respondent	Friendly to customers	Selling whole/retail price, fry fish to add value, livelihood
6 th respondent	Customers like fresh fish not overstayed fish	Discount, sell only fresh fish, livelihood

Source: Field data, 2018

The findings in Table 2 show that for awareness, the subtheme “friendly to customers” was dominant followed by subthemes of “I show fish to tourists”, “smile”, “new face in the fish market means a tourist”, “customers like fresh fish”, and “charge more to tourists”. This suggests that residents are aware about seafood as a tourism product when they are able to be friendly to tourists when they sell fish and show the fish to tourists. The findings further suggests that residents are aware of seafood as a tourism product when they are able to smile to tourists as they sell fish and another respondent uses “karibu” in Kiswahili language which means welcome. The ability to identify new faces in the fish market means that the new faces are tourists, and therefore feel that they are able to sell to tourists. The interview findings also suggest that awareness of seafood as a tourism product is when the fish vendors have the ability to know that customers like fresh fish

which means that tourists go to visit the fish market because they like fresh fish. Other fish vendors charge more to tourists, and thus contribute earnings which are crucial to their livelihood.

Table 2 also show findings of participation for the interviewed respondents who stated that they participate in seafood as a tourism product mainly for “livelihood” through “giving discounts”, “convincing” tourists to buy their fish which is “fresh and good”, and also offer “fish tasting to tourists”. Another respondent also stated that he “educates” tourists about fish while another respondent participates in seafood as a tourism product by selling “fried fish to add value” as well as sell fish on whole and retail prices.

In addition, one of the respondents pointed out that *“it will be good if there are fish festivals so that fish eating can be promoted as a tourism product”*. This implies that the subthemes identified in this study for participation by residents on seafood as a tourism product are “livelihood”, “giving discounts”, “convincing”, “fresh and good”, “fish tasting”, “educate”, “fried fish to add value”, and “sell fish on whole and retail prices”. The findings of this study differ from a study conducted in China by Su *et al* (2017) which showed that residents perceive and participate in fishing tourism by providing free fishing gear and barbecue appliances to tourists while in this study the residents mostly give discounts and provide fish tasting to tourists to buy the fish. The variation of results suggests that residents use various tactics to lure tourists to buy fish and each style is unique to the particular location and response of tourists. The findings of this study are different from Robinson and Hite (2015) in the USA which put emphasis on labeling of seafood. The variation in the results is due to the fact that in this study fish sellers use fish tasting and trust as a way of assuring the tourists that they sell fish which is fresh and good.

The findings of this study reveal that the awareness and participation behaviours of residents in their perception of seafood as a tourism product is contributed by many factors such as ability to identify tourists by face, being friendly, give discounts, build trust, livelihood and fish tasting. Therefore, these findings support TPB by Ajzen (1991, 1988) in that the behaviour of residents’ perception of seafood as a tourism product is influenced by awareness and participation.

5. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that awareness and participation are the core factors of residents’ perception of seafood as a tourism product in Dar es Salaam. In awareness, the subthemes that emerged from the interviewed respondents were “friendly to customers”, “I show fish to tourists”, “smile”, “new face in the fish market means a tourist”, “customers like fresh fish”, and “charge more to tourists”. For the core factor of participation, the subthemes that were highlighted by the respondents were “livelihood”, “giving discounts”, “convincing”, “fresh and good”, “fish tasting”, “educate”, “fried fish to add value”, and “sell fish on whole and retail prices”. Awareness and participation identified in this study as core factors of residents’ perception of seafood as a tourism product support the theory of planned behaviour which assumes that individual’s behaviour is underpinned by intention, subjective norms and perceived behaviour.

The outcome of this study can contribute to addressing economic growth which is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by linking seafood and tourism. Also at the national level, the tourism sector can use the information of this study to promote seafood as a tourism product in coastal areas of Tanzania. This study also provides insights on suggestions by one of the interviewee recommending fish festivals as a way of promoting seafood as a tourism product. The proposed recommendation can also assist to attract more residents to participate in seafood activities.

Limitations of the study is that this is a cross sectional design paper and therefore, future researchers can explore the possibility of conducting a quantitative study on the identified core factors of awareness and participation to analyze residents’ perception of seafood as a tourism product.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, W. (2013). "Leakages in the tourism systems: case of Zanzibar." *Tourism Review* **68**(1): 62-76.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). "The theory of planned behaviour." *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Process* **50**: 179-211.
- Araria, J.F., & Carmelo, J., & Leon. (2013). "Correcting for scale perception bias in tourist satisfaction surveys." *Journal of Travel Research* **53**: 403-417.
- Ardabili, F.S., Rasouli, E., Daryani, S.M., Molaie, M., & Sharegi, B. (2011). "The role of food and culinary condition in tourism industry." *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* **9**(6): 826-833.
- Candela, G., & Figini, P. (2012). "Definitions and Key concepts." *The Economics of Tourism Destinations*. 17-44. Retrieved from <http://www.springer.com/978-3-642-20873-7>
- Conner, M., & Armitage, C. (1998). "Extending the theory of planned behavior : A review and avenues for further research." *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* **28**(15): 1429-1464.
- Dolnicar, S., & Huybers, T. (2010). "Different tourists-different perceptions of different cities consequences for destination image measurement and strategic destination marketing." 127-146. <http://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1748&context=commpapers>
- Galvez, J.C.P., Guzman, T.L., Buiza, F.C., Viruel, M.J.M. (2017). "Gastronomy as an element of attraction in a tourist destination: the case of Lima, Peru." *Journal of Ethics Food*, **4**: 254-261.
- Gnanapala, W.K.A. (2015). "Tourist perception and satisfaction: Implications for destination management." *American Journal of Marketing Research* **1**(1): 7-19.
- Gortan-Carlin, I.P., & Krajnovic, A. (2016). "Music as a tourist product-The management and marketing model." In; Proceedings of the Management International Conference. 1-2 June, 2016, Pula, Croatia. pp. 207-220. Retrieved from <http://www.hippocampus.si/ISBN/978-961-6984-81-2/114.pdf>
- Grudda, M. (2010). "Understanding Visitor attitudes towards seafood and tourism in the Nelson/Marlborough and Golden Bay region in New Zealand to foster innovative sustainable forms of tourism." 1-187. <http://aut.researchgateway.ac.nz/bitstream/handle/10292/1237/GruddaM.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y>
- Hornig, J.S., & Tsai, C.T. (2012). "Constructing indicators of culinary tourism strategy: An application of Resource-Based Theory." *Journal of Travel and Tourism* **29**(8): 796-816.
- Hsu, F.C. (2014). "Food tourism: Consumer behaviour in relation to traditional food." 1-206: https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/data/UQ_351471/s42470676_phd_submission.pdf?Expires=1524723228&Signature=UMpgKNSLTnvLx00ZfflAhb~0cxzUhcDUftY9WCl2xbniSihflnA-HERmnX6SJDmMajBY9IemJ603OTPxJ9Bvet~UHtkPeVWHgJ9fMBPUinDuijveSAwgt0WPejW~jcHrTmKRtvHbeqhfDvuuEHdWfMWwJAGizlVSiFMMHn8vUYifBD7hmBW~r7Z978DMiDYtprkoNnNYUNMliandS14Ki1QZgr8fsjXihAl5nweiMhPmEB5kJV0VtSenWNwftMWQTQCzzeTY4ASnpsq-X8Qv4xkWkC-2~r5ODCinz9qRzFkjpmpihdbddolzDhO8B3eDO5WAhzpPNbFnggrEks1AVA__&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJKNBj4MJBjNC6NLQ
- Jani, D. (2016). "Local attendees' perception of festival impacts: A factor-cluster analysis approach to Zanzibar International Film Festival." In; Proceedings of the International Conference on Tourism and Hospitality Innovations in Developing Countries (ICTHI-DC). 1-2 August, 2016, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania 395: pp. 206-221. Retrieved from C:\Youtube\Tourism Conference Proceedings APRIL 2017.pdf
- Jani, J., & Naji, L.S. (2017). "Exploring the Satisfiers and Dissatisfiers in Airline Customers: A Tanzanian Perspective." In Proceedings ATLAS Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 35-36. <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>

- Kafle, N. (2014). "Nature based tourism and visitor experiences in Chitwan National Park." 1-64.
https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/70910/THESIS_Kafle_Nabin.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Kozhevnikova, V. (2016). "New tourism product development case: Guided tour to Savonlinna for Saimia International Students." 5-53.
https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/106869/Kozhevnikova_Varvara.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Kumar, C.P., Sakthivel, R., & Ramanathan, H. (2013). "Local residents perception and attitude towards model tourism village Kumbalangi Kerala." *Journal of Contemporary Research in Management* 8(1): 59-67.
- Lamb, C., Hair, J., McDaniel, C. (2014). "*Principles of Marketing*." Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Maliva, N.S. (2016). "*Women's Participation in Tourism in Zanzibar*." Wageningen, Netherlands. ISBN 10.18174/389702
- Maliva, N.S., & Jani, D. (2017). "Segmenting inbound tourist using destination image : Evidence from Tanzania."
In Proceedings ATLAS
Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 54. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Mas M. I. (2015). "The fishing footprints of a tourism-based economy: displaying seafood consumption from local to distant waters in the Balearic Islands." *Journal of Political Ecology* 22: 212-238.
- Mbilinyi, D.B. (2017). "Investigation of tourists' total dining experiences in Tanzania: An inbound tourists' perspective."
In Proceedings ATLAS
Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 57.
<http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Meng, F., Zhang, P., & Pan, B. (2015). "Examination of an extended theory of planned behaviour model on overseas tourism shopping." *Tourism Travel & Research Association: Advancing Tourism Research Globally* 23: 1-6.
<https://scholarworks.umass.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1113&context=ttra>
- Mgonja, J.T., Backman, K.F., & Backman, S.J. (2014). "Assessment of international tourists' perception on local foods in Tanzania." *Health, Education & Human Development Award* 1.
https://tigerprints.clemson.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1004&context=hehd_awards
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2016). "Promoting Kitulo National Park as a Wildflower Tourism Destination in Tanzania: Analysis of Media Channels and Gender among Domestic Tourists." *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development* 5(10): 388-393.
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2017a). "Influence of media and income on domestic tourists visiting Udzungwa National Park, Tanzania."
In; Proceedings ATLAS
Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 60-61. <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2017b). "Tourism and Global Citizenship: A perspective of Domestic Tourists visitation profile and social media in Udzungwa National Park, Tanzania." In; Proceedings of the International Conference on Tourism, Ethics and Global Citizenship: Connecting the Dots. 3-6 July, 2017, Apeldoorn, the Netherlands 96: pp. 57.

<https://saxion.nl/wps/wcm/connect/ae736801-f0f0-484e-81f8-935287550c72/Proceedings+booklet.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=ae736801-f0f0-484e-81f8-935287550c72>

- Mkwizu, K.H. (2017c). "Promotion of National Parks for Domestic Tourism in Tanzania." *The International Journal of Business & Management* 5(7): 146-150.
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2018). "Media and source markets for domestic tourism in Tanzania: Study of Kitulo National Park." *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development* 7(12): 107-112.
- Quintero, A.O. (2018). "A cartography of dispossession : assessing spatial reorganization in state-led conservation in Saadani, Tanzania." Retrieved from http://jpe.library.arizona.edu/volume_25/OrozcoKing.pdf
- Rajesh, R. (2013). "Impact of tourist perceptions, destination image and tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty : A conceptual Model." *Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural* 11(3): 67-78.
- Robbins, S.P. (2005). "*Organizational Behaviour.*" New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Robinson, D., & Hite, D. (2015). "An analysis of tourists' preferences and perceptions for Gulf Coast seafood: Does labeling matter ?" <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/bitstream/196838/2/For%20SAEA%202015.pdf>
- Schultz, J.R. (2014). "Applying the theory of planned behaviour to participation in sustainable tourism certificate programs." 2-117.
<http://cdmbuntu.lib.utah.edu/utills/getfile/collection/etd3/id/2917/filename/2923.pdf>
- Sing'ambi, E. and Lwoga, N.B. (2017). "Heritage attachment and domestic tourists decision to visit Bagamoyo historic town." In; Proceedings ATLAS Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 88-89. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Solomon, M.R. (2001). "*Consumer Behaviour: Buying, Having, Being.*" (5th ed.), New Jersey: NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Stevenson, A., & Waite, M. (2012). "The concise Oxford English Dictionary." (12^e), Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Su, M.M., Wall, G., & Wang, S. (2017). "Yujiale fishing tourism and island development in Changshan Archipelago, Changdao, China." *Island Studies Journal* 12(2): 127-142.
- Swarbrooke, J., & Horner, S. (1999). "*Consumer Behaviour in Tourism.*" Butterworth Heinemann, Oxford.
- Tanzania Coastal Management Partnership. (2001). "Tanzania Coastal Tourism Situation Analysis." http://www.tanzaniagateway.org/docs/Tanzania_coastal_tourism_situation_analysis.pdf
- Ukwayi, J.K., Eja, E., & Unwanede, C. (2012). "Assessment of tourist on service quality in the hospitality industry in Cross River State." *Journal of Sociological Research* 3(2): 1-10.
- Wilbard, J., & Jani, D. (2017). "Competitiveness in Hospitality Industry and Destination Image : Tanzania Style." In Proceedings ATLAS Africa conference on Africa's Tourism and Travel Competitiveness: Opportunities and Challenges. 7-9 June, 2017, Eldoret, Kenya 100: pp. 100. <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-WOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- World Travel and Tourism Council. (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.wttc.org/-/media/files/reports/economic-impact-research/regions->
- Xu, J.B. (2010). "Perception of tourism products." *Tourism Management* 31: 607-610.